

IMPACT OF GRAMEEN BANK'S EIGHTEEN DECISIONS ON THE LIVELIHOOD STATUS OF BORROWERS: A CHATTOGRAM PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Grameen Bank's eighteen decisions on the livelihood status of its borrowers. Grameen Bank, renowned for its microcredit and social development initiatives, implemented the eighteen decisions as a guiding framework to empower borrowers and promote sustainable development. Through a quantitative research approach, data were gathered from a sample of Grameen Bank borrowers, focusing on their perceptions and experiences regarding the adoption and implementation of the Eighteen Decisions. The findings reveal the multifaceted effects of these decisions on various aspects of borrowers' livelihoods, including economic empowerment, social cohesion, and personal development. The study highlights the significance of microfinance interventions in promoting holistic development and offers insights for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders in the area of microfinance and alleviation of poverty.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Grameen Bank, Livelihood status, Microcredit, Poverty alleviation.

1. Introduction

Microcredit, a financial mechanism aimed at providing small loans to the economically disenfranchised, has emerged as a transformative force in global development. The role of microfinance in poverty alleviation and economic development has been widely recognized across the globe, particularly in developing countries where financial exclusion remains a significant challenge (Armendáriz & Morduch, 2010). Among the pioneering institutions in microfinance, Grameen Bank of Bangladesh has gained international recognition for its innovative approach to

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providing financial assistances to the rural poor. Established by Nobel Laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus in 1983, Grameen Bank has transformed the conventional banking system by offering collateral-free loans to marginalized communities, with a primary focus on empowering women, fostering entrepreneurship and catalyzing self-sufficiency (Barua & Khaled, 2023). At the core of its operations lies a set of principles known as the Eighteen Decisions (listed in the Appendix), which serve as a guiding framework for borrowers to achieve socioeconomic progress. These decisions encompass a wide range of developmental aspects, including social, economic, health, and environmental concerns, promoting a holistic approach to financial inclusion and community development. Despite the widespread acknowledgment of the bank's contribution to the society in the form of poverty reduction and gender empowerment, the real impact of its Eighteen Decisions on borrowers' livelihood status warrants deeper examination.

Over the years, microfinance institutions (MFIs) have evolved as a critical tool for financial empowerment, yet debates persist regarding their long-term sustainability and transformative potential (Bhuiya et al., 2016). While financial access alone may not guarantee poverty alleviation, the holistic development strategy embedded within Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions offers a unique perspective on how structured guidance, coupled with financial support, can lead to substantial improvements in the quality of life. These decisions encourage borrowers to embrace social responsibility, foster entrepreneurship, ensure proper health and hygiene practices, and invest in education for their children. The interconnection between financial literacy, responsible borrowing, and sustainable livelihood practices is particularly evident in the Grameen model, as it goes beyond monetary assistance to emphasize behavioral change and collective progress (Ali et al., 2024). By incorporating aspects such as discipline, unity, and hard work, the Eighteen Decisions aim to instill long-term resilience in borrowers, enabling them to escape from the vicious cycle of poverty. However, the degree of compliance with these principles and their actual influence on borrowers' socioeconomic mobility remain key areas for investigation, as various external and internal factors may affect their implementation and outcomes.

MFIs, particularly exemplified by Grameen Bank, have emerged as potent agents in the global fight against poverty. It has continuously extended its services to a growing number of borrowers. The following figure illustrates the trends in the total number of borrower members of Grameen Bank over the past five years (Grameen Bank, 2025). This data provides valuable insights into the bank's outreach, growth trajectory, and its role in supporting financially disadvantaged communities.

Figure 1: Total Number of Borrowers (in Million)

Figure-1 illustrates the upward trend in the total number of borrower members of Grameen Bank from February 2021 to February 2025. The data reveal a consistent increase in membership, reflecting the growing outreach of microfinance services in Bangladesh. In February 2021, the total number of borrower members stood at 9.4 million, which then increased to 9.61 million in February 2022. This growth accelerated significantly in the following year, reaching 10.32 million in February 2023, indicating a substantial expansion in borrower inclusion. The trend continued with a rise to 10.52 million in February 2024 and further to 10.68 million in February 2025. This steady increase suggests that Grameen Bank's microfinance initiatives are effectively attracting more borrowers over time, likely due to the institution's efforts in financial inclusion, poverty alleviation, and economic empowerment. The sustained growth highlights the bank's continued relevance and impact on marginalized communities, reinforcing its role in providing accessible credit to those in need.

Therefore, the importance of this research stems from its ability to provide valuable insights, not only for Grameen Bank but also for the wider microfinance sector and its role in combating poverty. Understanding how these decisions translate into tangible improvements in the livelihoods of borrowers can inform the design and implementation of similar initiatives globally. As the embark on this exploration, it acknowledges the pioneering spirit of Grameen Bank and the transformative power embedded in decisions crafted with the vision of a prosperous and empowered community. The study is an exploration of how these decisions, each a unique facet of empowerment, weave together to create a tapestry of sustainable livelihoods and empowered communities.

1.1 Objective of the Study

Understanding the impact of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions requires a multidimensional approach, assessing not only economic indicators but also social empowerment, health improvements, and environmental consciousness among borrowers. While previous studies have focused extensively on microfinance's role in poverty reduction, fewer have explicitly examined the behavioral and attitudinal shifts brought about by structured financial programs like those of Grameen Bank. By analyzing the lived experiences of borrowers, this research aims to explore the multifaceted consequences of these decisions. By meticulously examining each decision, this research aims to unravel the intricate connections between adherence to these principles and the overall improvement in the quality of life for Grameen Bank borrowers.

1.2 Research Questions

This study is guided by two research questions aimed at exploring the impact of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions on the livelihood status of borrowers in the Chattogram region. First, it seeks to identify the principal components that effectively summarize the underlying dimensions of the Eighteen Decisions in relation to borrowers' livelihood outcomes. Second, the research investigates which specific sets of Grameen Bank's Decisions serve as significant predictors of improved livelihood status among borrowers in the region. Together, these questions aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the structured framework of the Eighteen

Decisions translates into measurable impacts on the livelihood status of borrowers in the context of Chattogram.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The Grameen Bank, with its innovative approach encapsulated in the Eighteen Decisions, represents a pioneering model that extends beyond traditional economic parameters. This study holds immense significance in evaluating the impact of these decisions on the livelihood status of borrowers, contributing valuable insights to the broader discourse on microfinance and poverty reduction. Recognizing poverty as a multidimensional challenge, the research delves into education, health, environmental, and social dimensions, painting a comprehensive picture of the interventions' efficacy. Moreover, the findings are poised to be not only pertinent to Bangladesh but also transferable to other nations facing similar socio-economic conditions. This contextual relevance contributes to the global discourse on poverty alleviation and microfinance as catalysts for positive change.

1.4 Rationale behind the regional focus

The selection of Chattogram as the focal region for this study is driven by its unique socio-economic and geographic characteristics, which make it a compelling case for examining the impact of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions. As the second-largest division in Bangladesh and a major commercial hub, Chattogram encompasses a diverse population, ranging from urban centers to remote rural communities, many of whom rely on microfinance to improve their livelihoods. The region has a long-standing presence of Grameen Bank operations, providing a substantial base of experienced borrowers who have been engaged in micro-credit activities for several years. This context allows for a rich exploration of how sustained exposure to the Bank's principles influences various aspects of life, including income generation, education, health, and social empowerment. Additionally, the researcher's personal familiarity with the area enhances access and contextual understanding, thereby ensuring deeper insight into the lived experiences of the respondents.

2. Literature Review

A considerable number of research has been dedicated to examining the impact of microcredit on poverty reduction in Bangladesh, with a consensus in many studies, including those by Khandker and Hussain (2013), Schroeder (2012), and Tesfay (2009), indicating a significant role in alleviating poverty. Armendariz and Morduch (2005) argue that assessing the impact of microcredit necessitates accounting for measurable factors such as age, profession, education, and experience, while also considering immeasurable characteristics like entrepreneurial ability and broader contextual factors like political upheavals or economic conditions during loan periods. Islam (2011) contends that more substantial benefits emerge from medium to long-term participation in microcredit programs compared to short-term engagement, emphasizing the importance of program duration. Additionally, Chemin (2008) conducted an evaluation of microcredit program participation, finding positive impacts on participants' expenditure patterns and increased enrollment of their children in schools. Ara et al., (2020) also explores the economic implications of sustained engagement in the microcredit program for poverty alleviation in

Bangladesh. The result of their study indicates that continuous participants derive greater advantages compared to those who discontinue their participation.

Borbora and Sarma (2020) assessed the influence of microfinance on the income and well-being of its clients and indicated that participants in microfinance experience comparatively better consumption expenditure and income than non-participants. Islam et al., (2014) conducted an examination of the influence of microcredit on reducing poverty by surveying 100 microcredit receivers from Grameen Bank, ASA and BRAC. Utilizing structured questionnaires, they discovered that these Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) contribute significantly in reduction of poverty by fostering employment opportunities and improving the quality of living standards through enhanced education, better healthcare facilities, and increased expenditure on health. Swain and Floro (2012) conducted an analysis using cross-sectional data to evaluate the effectiveness of India's Self-Help Group (SHG) model in mitigating poverty and economic vulnerability. By applying propensity score matching (PSM), they examined the extent to which participation in SHGs influenced the financial stability of enrolled households. Their findings demonstrated that households engaged in SHGs experienced a notable decline in economic vulnerability within the first year of membership, highlighting the program's effectiveness in fostering financial resilience.

Choudhury et al. (2017) conducted an in-depth analysis of the effects of microfinance programs on household financial well-being by examining data from borrowers who had successfully completed at least three loan cycles. Their study revealed a substantial and statistically significant improvement in key economic indicators, including household income, overall expenditure, and savings accumulation. These findings highlight the critical role of sustained microfinance engagement in fostering long-term financial stability and economic resilience among borrowers.

Similarly, Boonperm et al. (2013) assessed the impact of Thailand's Village Fund (VF) initiative on household income and expenditure by employing both propensity score matching (PSM) and a fixed-effects model. Their research demonstrated that participation in the VF program led to a 1.4% increase in income and a 3.5% rise in overall household spending. Notably, the most pronounced impact on expenditure was observed among households in the lower-income quantiles, underscoring the pro-poor nature of the initiative. This suggests that targeted financial interventions such as VF can be instrumental in reducing income disparities and improving the economic conditions of marginalized populations.

Hossain (2012) conducted an extensive study utilizing a semi-structured questionnaire to survey 208 individuals who had taken loans from BRAC's microfinance program. The research findings indicated that microfinance had a substantial and positive influence on several socio-economic aspects of the borrowers' lives. Specifically, it contributed to improvements in their occupational stability, increased overall household expenditure, and facilitated better financial management through enhanced savings. Additionally, access to microcredit led to employment generation, allowing borrowers to create new job opportunities either for themselves or within their communities. Furthermore, microfinance loans played a crucial role in upgrading housing conditions, enabling borrowers to invest in more

secure and improved living environments. These findings underscore the multidimensional benefits of microfinance, extending beyond immediate financial relief to long-term socio-economic advancement.

In a separate but complementary study, Khandker et al. (2015) explored the long-term implications of microcredit on household welfare, offering valuable insights into the sustainability of its effects. Utilizing panel data collected from 87 villages across rural Bangladesh, they conducted a rigorous assessment of microfinance's prolonged impact on multiple economic indicators. Their analysis revealed that sustained access to microcredit led to a notable increase in household per capita income and expenditures, thereby contributing to poverty alleviation.

Despite the widespread recognition of microfinance as a tool for poverty alleviation, several studies have raised concerns about the reliability of its impact. Banerjee (2013) argues that there is insufficient empirical evidence to establish a clear link between microcredit and significant improvements in income levels or consumption patterns among individuals who have participated in microfinance programs for one to three years. This skepticism suggests that while microfinance may provide short-term financial relief, its ability to foster sustainable economic growth and long-term financial stability remains debatable.

Further reinforcing this viewpoint, Banerjee et al. (2015) conducted an in-depth analysis of microcredit's influence on household consumption by categorizing expenditure into two types: "durable goods" and "temptation goods." Their findings indicated that microfinance borrowers exhibited an increase in spending on durable goods, which typically include long-term household assets such as furniture and appliances. However, expenditures on temptation goods—items often associated with discretionary or non-essential spending, such as alcohol, tobacco, or luxury items—declined among borrowers. While this shift in spending behavior could be interpreted as an indicator of improved financial decision-making, the study found no substantial impact on critical social indicators such as health, education, or women's empowerment. These findings suggest that while microfinance may influence consumption patterns, its broader social effects remain inconclusive.

The debate surrounding microfinance's effectiveness is further complicated by differing scholarly perspectives. Some researchers, such as Copestake et al. (2001), argue that while microfinance provides benefits to the poor, it does not necessarily uplift the most impoverished segments of society. This suggests that microcredit programs may be more effective for individuals who are already slightly above the extreme poverty line, rather than for those in the most vulnerable socio-economic conditions. Meanwhile, contrasting viewpoints highlight microfinance's potential negative consequences, including the exploitation of women borrowers, as many are encouraged or in some cases pressured to take on debt without having full autonomy over their financial decisions. Copestake (2002) also points to other adverse effects, such as unchanged or even worsening poverty levels, widening income disparities, increased workloads for borrowers, and even a rise in child labor as families struggle to meet repayment obligations. Additionally, critics argue that microfinance can create a cycle of dependency, where borrowers continuously rely on credit instead of achieving sustainable economic self-sufficiency, thus hindering broader local

economic and social development. These concerns highlight the need for a more nuanced approach to microfinance, ensuring that it serves as a genuine catalyst for economic empowerment rather than a mechanism that perpetuates financial vulnerability.

Although debates persist regarding the effectiveness of microfinance, it remains widely recognized as a powerful instrument for poverty alleviation and economic empowerment. Extensive empirical research provides substantial evidence supporting its positive role in improving the financial and social well-being of borrowers. A study by Bhuiya et al. (2018) investigates how microfinance program participation influences health service usage and health-seeking behavior. Their findings reveal that participation in the program significantly improves different health care issues. Another study by Tekie et al. (2023) examined the role of the Saving and Micro-Credit Program (SMCP) in enhancing the livelihoods of its participants. Their research revealed a statistically significant relationship between the duration of a client's membership in the program and their average income levels. This finding underscores the importance of sustained engagement with microfinance services, as longer participation appears to yield more substantial financial benefits. Clients who remained in the program for extended periods demonstrated higher income growth, suggesting that continued access to financial resources, coupled with the accumulation of experience and financial discipline, plays a crucial role in fostering economic stability and upward mobility.

Access to financial services is a critical factor in economic development, especially for marginalized communities. Grameen Bank's microfinance model provides collateral-free loans to the rural poor, enabling them to engage in income-generating activities. Studies have shown that borrowers experience significant improvements in their economic status. For instance, Khandker (2005) found that microfinance participants had higher household incomes and asset accumulation compared to non-participants. Similarly, a study by Pitt and Khandker (1998) reported that female borrowers experienced a 20% increase in household consumption, indicating improved economic well-being.

Rahman and Hossain (1988) highlight that Grameen Bank's credit programs not only raise the income levels of rural poor communities but also contribute to a fairer distribution of income among participants, enabling them to pursue entrepreneurship through microloans. A key obstacle to women's entrepreneurial development is gender discrimination, which must be addressed to foster agricultural progress and rural development (Sen, 1987), which emphasizes expanding individuals' capabilities and agency. Additionally, empirical research shows that when women control resources, their households experience improved well-being (Doss, 2006; Hoddinott & Haddad, 1995; Quisumbing & Maluccio, 2003).

Hashemi et al. (1996) found that women who participated in Grameen Bank's microfinance programs exhibited a higher likelihood of engaging in household decision-making, demonstrating increased agency over financial and familial matters. Additionally, these women experienced enhanced mobility and heightened political awareness, suggesting that microfinance extends beyond economic benefits to promote broader social empowerment. This transformation is further bolstered by

Grameen Bank's distinctive group lending methodology, which not only provides financial access but also cultivates a strong sense of solidarity and collective responsibility among borrowers. Armendáriz and Morduch (2010) highlight that this group-based approach fosters mutual support networks, encouraging women to share knowledge, advocate for their rights, and gain confidence in navigating both economic and social spheres. Consequently, microfinance serves as a platform for advancing gender equity by equipping women with the resources, skills, and community backing necessary to challenge traditional power structures and enhance their societal influence.

Health and education are integral components of the eighteen decisions. Borrowers are encouraged to ensure their families have access to clean drinking water, use sanitary latrines, and vaccinate their children. These initiatives have led to measurable improvements in health outcomes. Ahmed et al., (2001) reported that Grameen Bank members had better health indicators compared to non-members, including lower child mortality rates. In terms of education, the emphasis on schooling has resulted in higher enrollment rates among borrowers' children, contributing to long-term socio-economic development (Khandker, 1998).

Khadem (2024) explored the effects of Grameen Bank's microfinance on extremely poor women through in-depth interviews with ten participants. The study revealed that microfinance played a significant role in enhancing household income, as women were able to repay their weekly installments through business investments or support from family income. This financial support contributed to increased earnings and greater empowerment for many participants. Complementing these findings, Shahriar (2025) argues that while microcredit alone cannot eradicate poverty, it remains a vital component of an integrated strategy for sustainable development. Bangladesh's microfinance experience, particularly through Grameen Bank, offers critical insights for other nations aiming to implement effective poverty alleviation programs.

Despite its notable achievements, the Grameen Bank model has not been without its share of criticisms and challenges. While microfinance has been widely acknowledged as a tool for financial inclusion and poverty alleviation, some scholars argue that it is not a comprehensive solution for lifting individuals out of poverty. Bateman and Chang (2012) highlight the risks associated with an overdependence on microcredit, suggesting that access to small loans, without corresponding opportunities for sustainable economic growth, can lead to cycles of indebtedness rather than long-term financial stability. They argue that in many cases, borrowers take on loans to meet immediate consumption needs rather than investing in productive ventures, which limits the potential for wealth accumulation and meaningful economic progress.

Furthermore, concerns have been raised regarding the financial sustainability of MFIs and the challenges they face in maintaining a balance between social impact and financial viability. One of the key issues is the high repayment pressure placed on borrowers, which can, in some cases, result in distressing consequences. Karim (2011) examines instances where borrowers, particularly women, face immense social and economic pressure to meet repayment obligations, often leading to asset

depletion, heightened stress, or even coercion by peer groups in collective lending structures. The rigid repayment schedules imposed by many MFIs may not always align with the fluctuating incomes of borrowers, especially those engaged in informal or seasonal employment, further exacerbating financial strain.

Moreover, critics argue that while microfinance has helped many individuals improve their livelihoods, it does not necessarily foster large-scale economic transformation or address structural barriers to poverty reduction. Limited access to markets, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of complementary support services- such as business training and financial literacy, can hinder the effectiveness of microfinance initiatives. Some scholars advocate for a more integrated approach that combines microfinance with broader development strategies, including investments in education, healthcare, and skill development programs, to create a more enabling environment for sustainable economic growth.

2.1 Research Gap

The existing body of research on Grameen Bank and its impact on borrowers primarily focuses on the overall effectiveness of microcredit, with limited attention to the specific analysis of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions and their collective influence on the livelihood status of borrowers. While there are studies exploring individual components of microcredit programs, there is a notable research gap in comprehensively investigating how the combined implementation of these eighteen decisions contributes to the economic well-being, social development, and empowerment of the borrowers. This study aims to fill this gap by offering a detailed examination of the holistic impact of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions on the livelihood status of its borrowers, providing valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders in the area of microfinance and alleviation of poverty.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Population and sample size

The target population for this study consists of individuals who have been actively engaged in microcredit programs for a minimum of five years and reside in the Chattogram region of Bangladesh. The rationale behind selecting this specific group lies in their extensive experience with microcredit, which enables them to provide deeper insights into both its benefits and challenges. Given their prolonged involvement, these individuals possess firsthand knowledge of how microfinance influences economic activities, household decision-making, and overall well-being, making them well-suited to offer informed responses to the research questionnaire.

To ensure a fair representation of the population, the study employed a random sampling technique in selecting participants. Random selection enhances the reliability and generalizability of the findings by minimizing selection bias and allowing for diverse perspectives within the study group (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The demographic characteristics of the respondents, including age, gender, education level, occupation, and income status, are presented in detail in Table 1, providing a comprehensive overview of the sample composition. By considering a well-defined population and employing a robust sampling method, this study aims to capture a holistic understanding of the long-term impact of microcredit in the Chattogram region.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Measuring Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	40	10.40
	Female	345	89.60
	Total	385	100
Age (Years)	Up to 25	50	13
	26-40	200	52
	40 and above	135	35
	Total	385	100
Education	Not at all (illiterate)	85	22
	1-5 years (up to primary)	150	39
	6-10 year (up to secondary)	120	31
	More than 10 years (above secondary)	30	8
	Total	385	100
Family size	3 and less	50	13
	4-5	135	35
	6 and above	200	52
	Total	385	100

Source: Field survey, 2023

The table above presents detailed information about the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including gender, age, education, and family size. The data reveals several key trends: i) the overwhelming majority of respondents are women (89.60%), which aligns with the well-established fact that Grameen Bank primarily serves female clients, who tend to be more economically disadvantaged than men; ii) a significant proportion of the borrowers are young and middle-aged individuals, constituting 65% of the sample; iii) while the majority of respondents are literate (61%), their educational attainment is generally limited to primary school, indicating relatively low levels of formal education; iv) the data also shows the average family size of the respondents, reflecting typical household structures in the sample population.

To determine the sample size, Roscoe's Rule of Thumb (Sekaran, 2003) has been applied alongside the Google sample size calculator (www.calculator.net/sample-size-calculator), using a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, a 50% population proportion, and a total population size of 10,520,000. Based on these parameters, the required sample size for the study was calculated to be 385. Data collection began in the village of Chandanish and subsequently expanded to include

the areas of Anowara, Potiya, and Boalkhali. The data collection process took place over the months of September, October, November, and December in 2023.

3.2 Questionnaire Design and Measurement Scaling

Based on the above literature review, a structured questionnaire has developed incorporating the 18 Decisions related to Grameen Bank's microcredit activities for borrowers. The questionnaire has been divided into two sections. Section "A" collected demographic data from the respondents, including information such as name, gender, age, educational background, and number of family members. Section "B" focused on the 18 Decisions of Grameen Bank's microcredit program. Apart from the demographic questions, all other items in the questionnaire were dichotomous in nature. Respondents were asked to choose between two possible responses, represented by values of 0 or 1. For example, a question might inquire whether the respondent has benefitted from the microcredit program, with a response of 1 indicating a positive answer and 0 indicating no benefit.

3.3 Tools of Analysis

In this research, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0 and Microsoft excel has been used for data analysis. As methods for analyzing data, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), frequency, percentage, and binary logistic regression model have been used to examine the responses.

3.4 Reliability and Validity test

The study employs a more rigorous approach to assessing data and measurement reliability and validity. To measure internal consistency and reliability, Cronbach's Alpha is utilized, which tests whether all the items in the scale effectively measure a single construct. The results presented in Table 2 indicate a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.757 for the 18 items. In social science research, it is important to note that Cronbach's Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, with a value above 0.60 considered acceptable for ensuring the reliability of the scale (Cronbach, 1951; Malhotra, 2002). Therefore, an Alpha value of 0.757 is deemed to indicate good reliability for the questionnaire's measurement.

Table 2: Measurement of Reliability

Variables	Statistics
Number of Items	18
Cronbach's Alpha	0.757
N	385

Source: Authors' calculation

Validity refers to the extent to which the scores on a scale accurately reflect the true variations in the characteristics being measured, rather than being influenced by random or systematic errors (Malhotra, 2002). For this study, criterion validity has been emphasized. This type of validity ensures that different variables, such as demographic characteristics, behavioral aspects, and attitudinal measures, are simultaneously collected and accurately represent the intended constructs.

3.5 Econometric Model Specification

The binary logistic regression model was investigated in order to assess the factors (Grameen Bank's 18 Decisions) that determine the livelihood status of borrowers along with microcredit program in the study area. The response variable in the following binary response model is either binary or dichotomous. One of the two potential values, denoted for simplicity by 0 and 1, can be assumed by a person. Such observations include, for example, whether a person has benefited from the microcredit exercises ($LSB_i=1$) or not ($LSB_i=0$).

Based on Gujarati and Porter (2009), the following binary logistic model is estimated: The researcher finds the natural log of the equation as follows:

$$L_i = \ln = Z_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 D_1 + \beta_2 D_2 + \dots + \beta_{18} D_{18}$$

This implies that L , the log of the odds ratio (OR), is linear in D , and the parameters. The model denotes that if OR equals 1.00 or more, the relationship between the variables is positive; otherwise, if OR is less than 1.00, it is negative. It should also be noted that as ' LSB_i ' varies from 0 to 1, ' Z ' goes from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. In the same vein, the model for this study can be specified as follows:

$$LSB_{ij} = f(D_{1ij}, \dots, D_{18ij})$$

where, LSB_{ij} is a binary dependent variable. $LSB_{ij} = 1$, if there is an impact on livelihood status of borrowers, and $LSB_{ij} = 0$, if there is no impact.

Where, LSB_{ij} is the livelihood status of borrowers of village (i) in district (j); and D is the Decision of Grameen Bank.

Table 3: Coding of dependent variables affecting livelihood status of borrowers

Name of the Variables	Data Explanation*	Data Type	Condition Used
D ₁	Decision-01	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₂	Decision-02	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₃	Decision-03	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₄	Decision-04	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₅	Decision-05	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₆	Decision-06	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₇	Decision-07	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₈	Decision-08	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₉	Decision-09	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₀	Decision-10	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₁	Decision-11	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₂	Decision-12	Binary	Yes=1, No=0

D ₁₃	Decision-13	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₄	Decision-14	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₅	Decision-15	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₆	Decision-16	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₇	Decision-17	Binary	Yes=1, No=0
D ₁₈	Decision-18	Binary	Yes=1, No=0

*Listed in the Appendix

4. Empirical Findings and Analysis

4.1 Principal Component Analysis

In this study, a total of 18 variables were incorporated into the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to explore the underlying structure and relationships within the data. To ensure the validity of the PCA, the assumption that these variables are uncorrelated within the population was rigorously tested using Bartlett's test of sphericity. This statistical test examines whether the correlation matrix of the variables significantly differs from the identity matrix, which would indicate that the variables are indeed related and suitable for factor analysis. The successful application of this test is crucial, as it validates the appropriateness of performing PCA and confirms that the variables hold enough intercorrelations to extract meaningful components for further analysis. The result is shown in the following table:

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.726
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2809.442
	Df	153
	Sig.	.000

Source: Authors' calculation

Factor analysis is deemed suitable for this study due to the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.726, as indicated in Table 3. The KMO value falls within the acceptable range of 0.5 to 1.0, which suggests that the sample is adequate for conducting factor analysis (Hadi & Islam, 2015). Furthermore, the Chi-square test value is 2809.442, with 153 degrees of freedom, and it is highly significant at a 0.000 p-value, which is below the 1% significance level. This result strongly supports the use of factor analysis as an appropriate method for identifying underlying factors. Consequently, factor analysis provides valuable insights into the key variables that significantly influence the 18 Decisions of Grameen Bank, helping to better understand the impact of these decisions on borrowers' livelihood status. This statistical technique not only confirms the relevance of the variables but also aids in pinpointing the most influential factors contributing to the borrowers' socioeconomic outcomes.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Decision-01	4.912	27.286	27.286	4.912	27.286	27.286
Decision-02	2.120	11.779	39.066	2.120	11.779	39.066
Decision-03	1.874	10.410	49.476	1.874	10.410	49.476
Decision-04	1.404	7.801	57.277	1.404	7.801	57.277
Decision-05	1.188	6.599	63.876	1.188	6.599	63.876
Decision-06	1.002	5.566	69.442			
Decision-07	.930	5.165	74.607			
Decision-08	.786	4.367	78.974			
Decision-09	.696	3.864	82.838			
Decision-10	.629	3.494	86.332			
Decision-11	.489	2.714	89.046			
Decision-12	.408	2.264	91.310			
Decision-13	.337	1.872	93.182			
Decision-14	.282	1.569	94.751			
Decision-15	.279	1.549	96.300			
Decision-16	.257	1.430	97.729			
Decision-17	.230	1.280	99.009			
Decision-18	.178	.991	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

Source: Authors' calculation

As shown in Table 5, a principal component factor analysis was carried out on the 18 Decisions associated with Grameen Bank's influence on the livelihood status of its borrowers. This analysis resulted in the identification of a five-factor solution, which collectively accounted for 63.876% of the total variance. This means that these five factors captured a substantial proportion of the variability in the data, reflecting the most significant underlying dimensions that shape the impact of Grameen Bank's microcredit program on borrowers' livelihoods. By explaining such a large portion of the variance, these factors provide meaningful insights into the key elements driving changes in the economic and social status of the borrowers, highlighting the core components that influence their well-being and life outcomes.

Table 6: Component Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5
Decision-01	.174	.560	.381	-.095	.294
Decision-02	.628	.231	.092	-.523	.205
Decision-03	.335	.516	.410	.420	-.209
Decision-04	.359	.461	.196	-.019	-.033
Decision-05	.667	.429	.008	-.158	-.090
Decision-06	.490	.337	-.180	.126	.087
Decision-07	-.050	.227	-.351	.222	.779
Decision-08	.523	-.020	-.478	.299	.062
Decision-09	.116	.176	.098	.679	-.193
Decision-10	.623	-.059	-.458	.033	-.300
Decision-11	.515	-.142	-.567	.285	.070
Decision-12	-.371	-.336	.467	.418	.377
Decision-13	.613	-.571	.163	-.042	-.046
Decision-14	.729	-.282	.118	-.023	.278
Decision-15	.793	-.098	.083	-.088	.124
Decision-16	.566	-.107	.457	.190	-.077
Decision-17	.515	-.566	.329	.010	.093
Decision-18	.598	-.100	.072	.032	-.064

Source: Authors' calculation

Table 7: Uncorrelated Factors

Factor Name	Loaded factors	Initial Eigen Values	% of Variance	Cumulative (%)
1 st important factor	Decision-02, Decision-05, Decision-06, Decision-08, Decision-10, Decision-11, Decision-13, Decision-18, Decision-15, Decision-16, Decision-17, Decision-14	4.912	27.286	27.286
2 nd important factor	Decision-01, Decision-04, Decision-03	2.120	11.779	39.066
3 rd important factor	Decision-12	1.874	10.410	49.476

4 th important factor	Decision-09	1.404	7.801	57.277
5 th important factor	Decision-07	1.188	6.599	63.876

Source: Authors' calculation

The results presented in Table 7 show the factor loadings and their associated eigenvalues, percentage of variance explained, and cumulative variance for five uncorrelated factors derived from the principal component factor analysis of Grameen Bank's 18 Decisions. The first factor, which is the most important, consists of 12 decisions: Decision-02, Decision-05, Decision-06, Decision-08, Decision-10, Decision-11, Decision-13, Decision-18, Decision-15, Decision-16, Decision-17, and Decision-14. This factor has the highest initial eigenvalue of 4.912, explaining 27.286% of the total variance. This means that these 12 decisions together are the most influential in explaining changes in the livelihood status of borrowers, contributing significantly to the overall understanding of the variables under study. Cumulatively, this factor accounts for 27.286% of the variance on its own.

The second factor consists of three decisions: Decision-01, Decision-04, and Decision-03. This factor has an eigenvalue of 2.120, explaining 11.779% of the variance. While it is not as influential as the first factor, it still makes a notable contribution to the overall variance, with its cumulative percentage reaching 39.066% when combined with the first factor. This suggests that these three decisions together play a secondary but still significant role in shaping the livelihood outcomes of borrowers.

The third factor is represented by a single decision, Decision-12. It has an eigenvalue of 1.874, explaining 10.410% of the variance. While this factor explains a smaller portion of the variance compared to the first two, it still provides valuable insight into a specific aspect of the borrowers' livelihood status. The cumulative variance after including this factor increases to 49.476%.

The fourth factor is made up of Decision-09, with an eigenvalue of 1.404, explaining 7.801% of the variance. This factor is less significant in comparison to the first three but still contributes to the overall understanding of the data. After incorporating this factor, the cumulative variance reaches 57.277%.

The fifth factor consists of a single decision, Decision-07, with an eigenvalue of 1.188, explaining 6.599% of the variance. This factor has the smallest contribution, but when added, it increases the cumulative variance to 63.876%. This indicates that the five factors together explain a total of 63.876% of the variance in the data, suggesting that a significant proportion of the variation in the borrowers' livelihood status can be attributed to these five factors.

4.2 Binary Logistic Regression Analysis

Five independent components emerged from the factor analysis i.e. First important factor, Second important factor, Third important factor, Fourth important factor, and Fifth important factor. For the binary logistic regression analysis, these variables are chosen as the independent variables, and the dependent variable is the livelihood status of Grameen Bank's borrowers.

The analysis reveals that the 18 Decisions of Grameen Bank can be grouped into five distinct uncorrelated factors, with the first factor explaining the largest portion of the variance. These factors cumulatively account for 63.876% of the total variance, suggesting that they represent the key dimensions that influence borrowers' livelihood outcomes. The first factor, consisting of 12 decisions, plays the most crucial role, while the other factors provide additional insights into specific aspects of the borrowers' lives. Overall, the results highlight the multidimensional nature of Grameen Bank's impact on its clients.

Table 8: Summary of Binary Logistic Regression Analysis

Variables	Odds Ratio	Std. Error	z-value	P> z	95% Conf.	Interval
First important factor	\$2.989	\$1.680	\$1.950	\$0.051	\$0.993	\$8.994
Second important factor	\$1.639	\$0.894	\$0.910	\$0.365	\$0.562	\$4.777
Third important factor	\$0.439	\$0.096	-\$3.780	\$0.000	\$0.286	\$0.673
Fourth important factor	\$1.982	\$0.434	\$3.120	\$0.002	\$1.290	\$3.044
Fifth important factor	\$1.528	\$0.347	\$1.870	\$0.062	\$0.980	\$2.383
Observation = 385						
Wald $\chi^2(5) = 34.03$						
Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$						
Pseudo $R^2 = 0.0675$						

Source: Authors' calculation

In Table 8, the Pseudo R-Square value is 0.0675, and the Wald chi-squared statistic for 5 degrees of freedom is 34.03. This indicates that the overall model is statistically significant (Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$). The Pseudo R-Square value typically ranges from 0 to 1, with extreme values of 0 or 1 indicating a poor fit (Hu et al., 2006). Therefore, this model is deemed statistically significant and fits the data adequately, with a Pseudo R-Square of 0.0675.

In the table, the following findings are observed in relation to the Odds Ratios ((OR>1.00 is positive impact and OR<1.00 is negative impact) and their corresponding p-values for the factors: a) The first important factor has an Odds Ratio (OR) of 2.989161, with a p-value of 0.051. This p-value is below the 10% level of significance, suggesting that the first important factor has a positive and statistically significant impact. b) The second important factor has an Odds Ratio (OR) of 1.63907, with a p-value of 0.365. Since the p-value is greater than 10%, this factor is not statistically significant, indicating that it does not have a meaningful impact at the 10% level. c) The third important factor has an Odds Ratio (OR) of 0.438835, with a p-value of 0.000. This p-value is below 1%, and the OR is less than 1, indicating a negative and statistically highly significant impact. d) The fourth important factor has an Odds Ratio (OR) of 1.981886, with a p-value of 0.002. Since the p-value is below 1%, this factor is statistically significant and has a positive impact. e) The fifth important factor has an Odds Ratio (OR) of 1.527973, with a p-value of 0.062. This p-value is below 5%, suggesting that the fifth factor is

statistically significant, though it is a marginal effect compared to the highly significant factors. In summary, except for the second important factor, all other factors are statistically significant at various levels of significance, indicating their substantial influence on the outcomes being measured. The findings indicate that the all factors regarding the 18 Decisions of Grameen Bank have a positive impact on the livelihood status of borrowers, except the third important factor. In particular, there is a 2.99:1 chance that borrowers can improve their livelihood status by 2.99 units due to increase in 1 unit of first important factors of Grameen Bank's 18 Decisions and so on. Hence, it can conclude that most of the important factors have a significant positive relationship to improve the livelihood status of Grameen Bank's borrowers.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the impact of Grameen Bank's Eighteen Decisions on the livelihood status of its borrowers. The findings highlight the positive effects of these decisions in fostering economic empowerment, social cohesion, and personal development among borrowers. The decisions encapsulate a comprehensive framework aimed at empowering borrowers and fostering sustainable development. Through a synthesis of principles such as discipline, unity, and hard work, coupled with practical initiatives ranging from health and education to environmental stewardship and entrepreneurship, these decisions serve as a blueprint for improving the livelihood status of the borrowers. Among these decisions, the first factor emerges as the most significant, encompassing key aspects such as improving quality of life, environmental sustainability, family planning, and financial discipline. By adhering to these principles and implementing the associated initiatives, borrowers can achieve economic empowerment, social cohesion, and personal development. The findings also highlight the transformative potential of microfinance interventions guided by holistic principles, offering valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders in the field. The results suggest that Grameen Bank's micro-credit activities have not only contributed to economic improvements but have also fostered a sense of empowerment among women, enhanced their participation in decision-making, and promoted social cohesion within communities. Moving forward, it is imperative for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders to continue supporting and scaling up such initiatives to address poverty and inequality effectively. Through collaborative efforts and innovative approaches, it is possible to build upon the successes of microfinance interventions and create lasting positive change in the lives of millions around the world.

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Appendix

List of the Eighteen Decisions of Grameen Bank:

Decision-01	We shall reflect on the following four principles of Grameen Bank in every sphere of life to make it a prosperous organization through the members of the Center: Discipline, Unity, Courage, Hard Work.
Decision-02	We shall improve our quality of life by bringing prosperity to our families.
Decision-03	We shall arrange for safe accommodation. We shall build improved and durable houses at the earliest.
Decision-04	We shall cultivate vegetables throughout the year, meet our own nutrition needs by having plenty of them, and increase income by selling the same.
Decision-05	During the planting season, we shall plant as many seedlings as possible to protect the environment and create our own resources.
Decision-06	We shall plan to keep our families small by having maximum two children. If possible, one will be the priority. We shall ensure all types of vaccinations for our children.
Decision-07	We shall ensure education of all children of the members of the center and shall educate them in technical and higher studies.
Decision-08	We shall keep our environment clean and tidy and ensure health care for all members of our families.
Decision-09	We shall use Sanitary Latrine and clean our hands with soap.
Decision-10	We shall drink tube well water. We shall use pure water in every household work.
Decision-11	We shall avoid dowry in the marriage of our son and daughter, and shall not entertain child marriage. We shall confirm marriage registration.
Decision-12	We shall treat everyone well. We shall live together in family and in society.
Decision-13	We shall create new entrepreneurs to make our children self-reliant.
Decision-14	We shall always help each other. If anyone in the center falls in any danger, we shall rescue him from the danger together.
Decision-15	We shall be careful in conducting the transaction; we shall not transact without the passbook and shall keep the passbook with our own.
Decision-16	We shall regularly attend the center meeting and we pay back our loan regularly.
Decision-17	We shall pay attention to the savings and we shall save in the bank regularly.
Decision-18	We shall ensure discipline in our center. We shall do all the social work together.

